

Omnidirectional image unwrapping algorithm for seamless panorama image

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Abstract: In the realm of robotics, video surveillance, and virtual reality representation, a broader field of view holds significant value. The utilization of catadioptric vision systems plays a pivotal role in expanding this field of view. These systems excel in capturing images without necessitating camera movement, offering remarkable stability. However, it's important to note that the human visual system is inherently attuned to conventional 2D images rather than omnidirectional ones. Consequently, the need arises to transform omnidirectional images into a more familiar format. In response to this requirement, we propose a method that effectively converts omnidirectional images into equirectangular projection images, enabling a panoramic perspective. Our experimental results demonstrate the superiority of this algorithm, delivering exceptional outcomes with minimal distortion.

Keywords: Catadioptric lenses. Equirectangular Projection Method. Field of view, Omnidirectional Image, Unwrapping.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wide-angle cameras have seen a surge in popularity over the past few decades. This rise in demand for high field of view (FOV) is particularly notable in robotic vision systems and surveillance systems[1]. Among the various options available, 360-degree cameras, also known as omnidirectional cameras, offer the highest FOV while minimizing hardware requirements. Alternatively, achieving maximum FOV can involve deploying multiple cameras with narrower FOVs[2]. These cameras can seamlessly stitch together images to create panoramic views through image processing. However, it's important to acknowledge that this technique has its limitations. It relies on the physical repositioning of cameras, which demands time and involves mechanical assemblies and motors. These factors can introduce a degree of unreliability into the system[3].

The 360-degree cameras excel in providing a comprehensive view of the surroundings in a single capture, enhancing system reliability. To further extend the field of view, catadioptric vision systems utilize a combination of lenses and mirrors. In this configuration, a convex mirror is positioned opposite to the camera lens, ensuring alignment of the optical lens axis with the mirror's center[4][5]. This setup enables image capture without the need for camera movement, resulting in a highly stable system. Numerous 360-degree cameras with catadioptric lenses are readily available in the market. Figure 1 illustrates one such example of a 360-degree camera equipped with catadioptric lenses[6].

Figure1: Catadioptric lenses camera

The images obtained through a Catadioptric vision system offer a wealth of details but are subject to distortion resulting from the geometry of the non-uniform resolution mirror [7]. While resolution is excellent at the periphery, it degrades towards the center of the image. This uneven distortion adds complexity to the unwrapping process [8]. Moreover, the output image from this system typically appears in a circular format, which is not ideally suited for human visual perception. Human eyes are naturally predisposed to conventional 2D images rather than omnidirectional formats, necessitating the unwrapping of omnidirectional images[9][10][11].

To address this challenge, we present an algorithm designed to unwrap omnidirectional images, transforming them into panoramic images. The remaining paper is structured in the following way: Section 2 offers an overview of existing methods for unwrapping omnidirectional images, Section 3 provides a detailed step-by-step explanation of our proposed algorithm, Section 4 presents the results achieved through the implementation of the proposed system and finally, in Section 4, we draw our conclusions.

II. OMNIDIRECTIONAL IMAGE UNWRAPPING METHODS

The process of unwrapping omnidirectional images employs various techniques, including Cylinder Plane Unwrapping, Ground Plane Unwrapping, and Cuboid Panoramic Unwrapping[4][9][12]. Subsequently, these images can undergo further processing through methods such as Equirectangular Presentation (ERP), Cube Map Presentation, and Spherical Presentation. In the Equirectangular Presentation (ERP) method, the image is divided into two edges and a central portion, as illustrated in Figure 2. In the second method, omnidirectional images can be represented using the cube map approach, where each face of the cube corresponds to a distinct portion of the omnidirectional image. Figure 3 depicts the cube map representation method[6][13]. The sphere map representation of an omnidirectional image involves the conversion of the spherical image into multiple sub regions, each mapped to independent images, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 2: ERP image

Figure 3: Cube map representation

Figure 4: Sphere map representation

Through the unwrapping process, omnidirectional images can be transformed into rectangular images, making them suitable for a wide range of applications[9]. Some of these applications include computer vision tasks such as object recognition, object tracking, and efficient compression tailored for virtual and augmented reality scenarios[14].

There are three methods that yield results in the form of Equirectangular projection:

- A. *The Panomapping method* involves the selection of specific points within the omnidirectional image based on varying radii. These selected points are used to derive N coefficients through a polynomial function, and these coefficients are stored in a table known as the Panomapping table. During the unwrapping process, the values from this table are mapped to corresponding image pixel values
- B. *The Discrete Geometry Techniques (DGT) method* is grounded in image geometry principles[16][17]. It calculates the pixels on the cylindrical surface based on the size of the image center. Specifically, if the image circle's radius encompasses a 3×3 pixel area, then the pixels within that 3×3 region are considered informative, as depicted in Figure 5. However, a notable drawback of this method is the potential for high quantization error.

Figure 5: pixels inside the circle

- C. In the *Log Polar Mapping method* samples from the omnidirectional image are utilized to transform it from a Cartesian to a log-polar form using a spatially variant grid. This grid represents multiple small concentric circles. These N circles are subsequently unwrapped into panoramic images, transitioning them back to another Cartesian form.

The algorithm proposed here facilitates the conversion of omnidirectional images into the Equirectangular Projection (ERP) method[18]. An omnidirectional image is generated by mapping the surrounding environment into polar coordinates. The reverse procedure is undertaken within the image unwrapping algorithm, where the polar coordinates of the image are transformed back into Cartesian coordinates. Utilizing the azimuthal angle, the omnidirectional image is then translated into a panoramic image[19][20].

In the process of converting pixels from an omnidirectional image into a rectangular image, it is necessary to define the radius of the omnidirectional image and demarcate its inner and outer circles. The radius serves as a critical parameter in this conversion, primarily influencing the image's perimeter. The perimeter of the circle is used to encompass all the pixels within the image, and the area enclosed by this perimeter is subject to transformation through the unwrapping algorithm.

Because of the circular geometry of omnidirectional images, it's noteworthy that distortion is less pronounced at the image's boundary compared to its center. In the resulting unwrapped image, the x-axis of the rectangular image corresponds to the largest circumference of the original omnidirectional image[21][22].

The pixel coordinates of omnidirectional image are transformed into ERP image pixel coordinates (X,Y). The origin (0,0) of the omnidirectional image is placed at the centre of the panoramic image and the peripheral of the circular image is mapped into the X axis the ERP image. The process is repeated till all the pixels of the omnidirectional images are converted into the panoramic image[9][23].

While execution of the algorithm in real time, the pixel values of original image and the expected image are stored in the look up table. The appropriate interpolation method is used to get the required unwrapped image. The following equations are used to generate the panoramic images.[14][24]

$$X = R\cos(t), Y = R\sin(t),$$

$$R = \text{sqrt}(X^2 + Y^2) \text{ and } t = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{Y}{X}\right)$$

the height(H) and width(w) of the unwrapping image from pixel values of X, Y as shown in figure 6, Image unwrapping.

Figure 6: Image unwrapping

III. THE PROPOSED ALGORITHM

- Identify the center of the omnidirectional image and store it as "Center 1" while determining the inner circle of the image.
- If the image's center and the center of the circular image are not aligned, calculate a new center ("Center 2").
- Compare "Center 2" with "Center 1." If they are not identical, utilize the value of "Center 2."
- To determine the radii of the inner and outer circles, employ a threshold method and set the threshold value.
- Convert the image into a binary format based on pixel values using the threshold.
- Calculate the radius as the square root of the mean of the outer boundary values.
- Draw a line from the top of the image (position 0,0) to the center of the circle.
- Determine the x-axis value of 't,' which is equal to the perimeter of the outer circle.

- Apply rectangular-to-polar conversion, transforming each pixel value of the omnidirectional image using the equation $x=R\sin(t)$, $y=R\cos(t)$.
- Iterate through this process until all values of the original image are transferred into the rectangular image.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

This algorithm is implemented on the MATLAB R2022a platform and demonstrates robust performance. After implementation, the following results are obtained. The step-by-step process of image unwrapping is shown in Figure 7. In this section, we delve into the outcomes achieved through the utilization of the proposed single center of projection image unwrapping algorithm.

Figure 7: The unwrapping Process: i.Input image, ii. Image centre is obtained, iii.Mark inner circle. iv. Binary image. v. Mark outer boundry. vi. Obtain radius. vii.&viii. Unwrapping process. ix. Output panoramic image.

The radius, denoted along the 'Y Axis' of the panorama image, plays a crucial role, while the circular image's perimeter determines the length of the panorama image along the 'X Axis.' Radius computation involves taking the square root of the mean of the outer boundary values. Radius selection governs the extent of unwrapping, with a smaller radius yielding a smaller perimeter and, consequently, fewer image details; whereas a larger radius results in a larger perimeter and greater image detail. The significance of radius selection is illustrated in Figure 8, where radius values ranging from 0.5 to 2.5 are explored, each displaying the corresponding unwrapped output.

To examine the finer details of the unwrapped image, a high-pass image output is also provided, accentuating all the image edges distinctly. It's evident that increasing the radius captures more intricate details within the circle, aligning with the unwrapping process. Higher radius values lead to the preservation of greater levels of detail

Radius	Input	Unwrapped Panoramic Image	Detailed HPF image
0.5			
1			
1.25			
1.5			
1.75			
2			
2.5			

Figure 8: Selection of radius with output

V. CONCLUSION

This paper introduces a novel method for unwrapping omnidirectional images, leveraging the capabilities of the catadioptric omnidirectional vision system, which offers an expansive field of view. The implemented algorithm is straightforward and underscores the importance of meticulously selecting the radius. Our proposed algorithm effectively demonstrates that the pixel area beneath the circle corresponds to the panoramic view area. As a result, the key to success lies in the careful selection of the radius. The algorithm excels in delivering seamless panorama images with minimal distortion, affirming its effectiveness.

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